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Kinetics of β – Alanine Oxidation by Hexacyanoferrate (III) Ion in Alkaline Medium

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Abstract

Amino acids are protein building components that include both acid and base groups. β -Alanine was used in alkaline medium for the current investigation. β -Alanine is a naturally occurring β -amino acid, meaning that the amino group is connected to the β -carbon rather than the more common α -carbon for alanine. 3-aminopropanoic acid is the IUPAC designation for β -alanine. Unlike its homologue, α -alanine, it lacks a stereocenter. The kinetics of β -Alanine oxidation by alkaline Os (VIII), which was continuously regenerated by hexacyanoferrate (III) ion, were investigated in the 0.01- 0.07 M and 298 K - 318 K temperature ranges. The rate of reaction was determined to be zero with respect to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN}_6)]^{3-}$ and one with respect to Os (VIII).

Keywords

Kinetics, β -Alanine, oxidation, osmium (VIII), hexacyanoferrate (III).

Introduction

β -alanine is a non-proteogenic amino acid that is formed in the liver. Furthermore, people obtain β -alanine via the intake of foods such as chicken and pork⁹. β -alanine has been identified as the rate-limiting precursor to carnosine synthesis⁴ and it has been repeatedly proven to enhance carnosine levels in human skeletal muscle^{4,9}. The majority of amino acids are needed to produce proteins, however, β -alanine is utilised to make other compounds in the body. It is a component of carnosine and other compounds that have the potential to influence muscle growth and performance.¹⁰ In older persons, taking β -alanine orally enhances exercise capacity and delays muscular fatigue^{34,35,36}. However, it does not appear to aid in strength training³.

Objective of study

To investigate the kinetics of β -alanine oxidation by osmium (Os (VIII)) in an alkaline medium, with Os (VIII) being regenerated by hexacyanoferrate (III), focusing on determining the reaction order and the influence of temperature and reactant concentrations.

Review of Literature

Amino acids can have carboxylic, sulphonic, or other acid groups. The $-\text{NH}_2$ group can be found in any location in amino acids. In general, amino acids are commonly used in reference to α -amino acids derived from natural sources. Amino acids exist as zwitterions in solution^{11,12,13,14,15}.

In general, all amino acids are water soluble but insoluble in non-polar solvents such as ethers, benzene, and so on^{14,26}. The hexacyanoferrate (III) ion is distinct from other oxidants that have more than one electron equivalent^{17,18}. In acidic and alkaline environments, it is an inert substitute^{1,2,6,8,16}. As a result, the readily accessible and water-soluble hexacyanoferrate (III) ion is a very effective oxidant for a wide range of inorganic and organic molecules^{21,25,28,30,39,40}.

Main Text

Standardisation of osmium tetroxide

One g of OsO_4 glass tube was collected. It was broken up and placed in a beaker with 0.5 N of sodium hydroxide solution. Glass tubing fragments have been removed from the solution. These pieces were washed with distilled water many times in the same beaker until the solid was totally dissolved. The solution was then transferred to a 1 L measuring flask. Conductivity water was utilised to bring the volume of the solution up to the desired level after dissolving the solid OsO_4 solution. The strength of sodium hydroxide was

determined by titrating the solution against a reference solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate with phenolphthalein as an indicator. The OsO_4 solution was also iodometrically standardised^{19,20}.

λ_{max} of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III):

The absorbance of unreacted (0.001M) potassium hexacyanoferrate (III), which was to be used as the oxidant, was measured at different wavelengths using a double beam Biosync Teknology Spectrophotometer, model number BST 2800, and an Elico-Digital Spectrophotometer, model number CL-27. The absorbance vs wavelength graph was constructed. The value of max for potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) was 420 nm^{24,31}.

Molar absorption coefficient of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III):

The absorbance values of different [potassium hexacyanoferrate (III)] were measured at 420 nm

$$\epsilon = \frac{\text{ABSORBANCE}}{\text{CONCENTRATION}}$$

The molar absorbance coefficient for potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) at 420 nm was measured to be $990 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which corresponds to the quoted value ($1030 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)^{24,31,32,33}.

Measurement of the rate constants:

The reaction mixtures were created using standard techniques. A combination of the predicted substrate and NaOH contents was added to the reaction vessels. Standard NaCl solutions kept their ionic strength. A solution of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) in a volumetric flask of 250 mL was prepared. These were kept at the desired temperature in a thermostatic water bath with a 0.1°C precision. The reaction was started by adding the required amount of hexacyanoferrate (III) to the reaction mixture once it had attained temperature equilibrium, which took at least 20 to 30 minutes in all cases. The reaction mixture was promptly extracted and transferred to the spectrophotometer's sample tube using a 5 mL pipette. The absorbance of the reaction mixture at 420 nm was measured using a double beam Biosync Teknology Spectrophotometer, model number BST 2800 and an Elico-Digital Spectrophotometer, model number CL-27^{22,23,37}. The absorbance was measured quickly, with no interval between the removal of the reaction mixture and the recording of the results. To trace the course of the reaction until it was completed, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured over time. The reactions were found to be too sluggish to study in alkaline media in the absence of a catalyst. Without the use of a catalyst in alkaline media, the oxidation of β -Alanine took nearly a month to complete. Hence Os (VIII) catalyst was added to the reaction mixtures to speed up the reactions. It was observed that in the presence of an Os (VIII) catalyst, alkaline medium reactions may be completed in less than 4 to 5 hours. The absorbance versus time charts for more than two half-lives of the reactions were almost linear, indicating a zero-order reaction with potassium hexacyanoferrate (III). The slope of the linear plot between absorbance and time was calculated in each case. The following formula was used to compute the rate constant k_0 :

$$\text{Rate Constant } (k_0) = \frac{\text{Slope}}{990}$$

Fig. 1: Zero order plot for the oxidation of B-Alanine

with respect to hexacyanoferrate (III) was zero. Fig.1 depicts a representative plot. The observation that the k_o values remained unchanged with the change in the initial [hexacyanoferrate (III)] while the $t_{1/2}$ values increased with the change in the initial [hexacyanoferrate (III)] provided additional support to the zero order reaction. Table 2 shows the results.

Table 2: The values of k_o and $t_{1/2}$ at different initial [hexacyanoferrate (III)] in the oxidation of β -Alanine
Temperature=298K, $10^2[\beta\text{-Alanine}]=1.0\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $10^2[\text{OH}^-]=50\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^5\text{Os(VIII)}=1.50\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu=1.0\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

10^4 [Fe(CN) ₆] ³⁻ (mol dm ⁻³)	8.0	10.0	12.0	14.0	16.0
$10^5 k_o$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	2.1161	2.0525	2.1555	2.2979	2.1217
Half life period $t_{1/2}$ (minutes)	16.11	22.13	27.08	32.15	36.12

Dependence on [OH⁻]:

The graphs between k_o and [OH⁻] were straight lines. Fig. 2 depicts examples of these plots. The ten-fold variation in [OH⁻] for β -Alanine was explored at five different temperatures because greater [OH⁻] caused divergence from zero order behaviour. Table 3 contains a summary of the findings.

Table 3: Effect of [OH⁻] on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine.
 $10^2[\beta\text{-Alanine}] = 1.0\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{Fe(CN)}_6]^{3-} = 1.2\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $10^5\text{Os(VIII)} = 1.50\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 1.0\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Temp. (K)	$10^2[\text{OH}^-]$ (mol dm ⁻³)				
	1	3	5	7.5	10
	$10^5 k_o$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)				
298	1.03	1.36	1.74	1.98	2.85
303	2.02	2.95	3.65	4.96	5.88
308	3.48	4.19	5.5	6.98	8.23
313	5.55	6.98	8.86	10.65	13.23
318	10.62	11.85	13.25	15.45	17.98

Fig.2: k_o vs [OH⁻] plot for the oxidation of β - Alanine at 298K, 303K, 308K, 313K and 318K.

Dependence on [Os (VIII)]:

The oxidation of β -Alanine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) was studied at different [Os (VIII)] at constant concentrations of all other reagents. It was discovered that the plots between k_o and [Os (VIII)] for a ten-fold variation in the initial [Os (VIII)] were linear and almost passed through the origin, as shown in Fig. 3 for the Os (VIII) catalysed hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine in alkaline medium. Table 4 summarises the findings.

Table 4: Effect of [Os (VIII)] on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine.
 $10^3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [\beta\text{-Alanine}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $10^2 [\text{OH}^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Temp. (K)	$10^5 \text{ Os [VIII]} (\text{mol dm}^{-3})$				
	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	5.0
	$10^5 k_0 (\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1})$				
298	1.3	2.15	4.16	5.12	8.56
303	1.75	3.15	5.98	7.15	11.69
308	1.95	3.85	7.12	9.23	14.23
313	2.25	5.41	9.46	12.53	18.14
318	2.65	7.11	12.32	15.65	23.56

Fig.3: k_0 vs [Os (VIII)] plots for the oxidation of β -Alanine at 298K, 303K, 308K, 313K and 318K.

Dependence on [amino acids]:

The order of the reaction with respect to β -Alanine was determined by studying the effect of different [β -Alanine] on the values of k_0 at constant concentrations of all other reagents. Only a seven-fold change in the [substrate] was carried out in β -Alanine. Because of the large amounts of β -Alanine, complicated kinetics was observed, and the rate constants fell. The plot of k_0^{-1} versus [β -Alanine] $^{-1}$ was found to be linear in each case, with an intercept on the k_0^{-1} axis^{22,23,37}. Fig.4 demonstrate these graphs. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Effect of [substrate] on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine
 $10^3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^5 \text{ Os [VIII]} = 1.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $10^2 [\text{OH}^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Temp. (K)	$10^2 [\beta\text{-Alanine}] (\text{mol dm}^{-3})$				
	1	2	4	6	7
	$10^5 k_0 (\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1})$				
298	1.14	1.94	2.82	3.02	3.24
303	3.56	4.95	5.98	6.13	6.27
308	6.46	7.96	9.51	9.87	9.94
313	7.49	9.05	11.57	12.54	12.63
318	9.48	11.3	16.42	16.97	17.03

Y_1 = Product -1

Y_2 = Final Product

n = No. of molecules of H_2O

The aforementioned process clearly shows that product (1) is generated as indicated in Eq. (5) and is then oxidised to the appropriate keto acid (the end product) in a fast step under the experimental circumstances, which is confirmed by stoichiometry and product analysis.

Therefore, the rate of disappearance of Os (VIII) be derived as:

$$-\frac{d[\text{Os(VIII)}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})(\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COO})]^{2-} \quad (8)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{Os(VIII)}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{OsO}_3(\text{OH})_3]^- [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] [\text{OH}]^- \{K_1K_3 + K_2K_4\} \quad (9)$$

Again since

$$\begin{aligned} & [\text{OsO}_3(\text{OH})_3]^- \\ &= \frac{[\text{Os(VIII)}]_{\text{Total}}}{1 + K_2[\text{OH}]^- + K_2K_4 [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] [\text{OH}]^- + K_1K_3[\text{OH}]^- [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}]} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{d[\text{Os(VIII)}]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{k_1 (K_1K_3 + K_2K_4) [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] [\text{OH}]^- [\text{Os(VIII)}]_{\text{Total}}}{1 + K_2[\text{OH}]^- + K_2K_4 [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] [\text{OH}]^- + K_1K_3[\text{OH}]^- [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}]} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$k_o = -\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1K_2K_4 [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] [\text{OH}]^- [\text{Os(VIII)}]_{\text{Total}}}{1 + K_2K_4 [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] [\text{OH}]^-} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_o} = \frac{1}{2k_1[\text{Os(VIII)}]_{\text{Total}}} + \frac{1}{2k_1K_2K_4 [\text{OH}]^- [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] [\text{Os(VIII)}]_{\text{Total}}} \quad (13)$$

Eq.(13) agrees with the observed linear plot of k^{-1} and $[\beta\text{-Alanine}]^{-1}$ in Fig. 4. The intercept (I) and slope (S) of these plots are obtained by Equations (14) and (15), respectively.

$$\text{Intercept} = \frac{1}{2k_1[\text{Os(VIII)}]_{\text{Total}}} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{1}{2k_1K_2K_4[\text{OH}^-][\text{Os(VIII)}]_{\text{Total}}} \quad (15)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} = K_2K_4[\text{OH}^-] \quad (16)$$

parameters for the β -Alanine amino acid. The activation energy and entropy values were determined using the slope and intercept values of the Arrhenius plot (Fig.5), which was practically linear for β - Alanine⁷.

In view of Eq. (6) and valid assumptions

$$K_2 K_4 \gg K_1 K_3 \text{ and}$$

$$1 + K_2 K_4 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}] \gg K_2 [\text{OH}^-] + K_1 K_3 [\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-COOH}]$$

Eq. (11) reduces to Eq. (12)

Table 7:The values of $[\text{substrate}]^{-1}$ and k_o^{-1} for the Os (VIII) catalysed hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine at different temperatures.

$$10^3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}, 10^5 [\text{Os (VIII)}] = 1.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}, \\ 10^2 [\text{OH}^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ and } \mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}.$$

Temp. (K)	[SUBSTRATE] ⁻¹ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³)				
	100	50	25	16.66	14.285
	10 ⁻³ k _o ⁻¹ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s)				
298	87.41258741	51.54639	35.46099	33.11258	30.8642
303	28.08988764	20.20202	16.72241	16.31321	15.94896
308	15.47987616	12.56281	10.51525	10.13171	10.06036
313	13.35113485	11.04972	8.643042	7.974482	7.917656
318	10.54852321	8.849558	6.090134	5.892752	5.871991

Table 8: The slope (S) and intercept (I) values for the β -Alanine hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation catalysed by Os (VIII).

Substrate	Temperature (K)	Intercept (I)	Slope (I)
β -Alanine	298	20.5226	0.6593
	303	13.5869	0.1425
	308	9.0839	0.0647
	313	7.1023	0.0652
	318	5.0613	0.0580

Table 9: The values of K_2 , K_4 , and k_1 for the Os (VIII) catalysed hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine at different temperatures.

Substrate	Temperature (K)	K_2 ($\text{mol}^{-1}\text{dm}^3$)	K_4 ($\text{mol}^{-1}\text{dm}^3$)	k_1 (s^{-1})
β -Alanine	298	24.0	25.9398	1624.2256
	303	27.0	70.6271	2453.3435
	308	30.0	93.6002	3669.4958
	313	36.0	60.5172	4693.3153
	318	43.0	40.5878	6585.9232

Table 10: The ΔH and ΔS values correspond to Os (VIII) catalysed hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine.

Substrate	ΔH (k J mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (k J mol ⁻¹)
β -Alanine.	54.441	- 0.8941

Conclusion

The following are the important features of the Os (VIII) catalysed hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of β -Alanine:

1. The reaction has a zero order in regard to hexacyanoferrate (III).
2. The reaction rate with reference to catalyst is one because the k_0 vs [Os (VIII)] plot is linear and almost reaches the origin.
3. As $[\text{OH}^-]$ levels rise, consequently does the rate of oxidation.
4. The linearity of the k_0^{-1} vs $[\text{substrate}]^{-1}$ plot results in a positive k_0^{-1} axis intercept.
5. The rate of oxidation increases with increasing ionic strength, and the $\log k_0$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ plot suggested that the reaction occurred between ions with similar charges.

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